

Patient and System-Level Delays in Diagnosis and Treatment of Invasive Cervical Carcinoma: Findings from two Tertiary Centers in Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Cervical cancer remains a major preventable malignancy in Bangladesh, with late presentation often resulting from delays in diagnosis and treatment. The study aimed to describe patient- and system-level delays in the diagnosis and treatment of invasive cervical carcinoma among women managed at tertiary-care centres in Bangladesh. **Methods % Materials:** This descriptive observational study was conducted from January to June 2008 in the oncology units of the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology at Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University and Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Dhaka. Thirty admitted women with histologically confirmed invasive carcinoma of the cervix were included. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and clinical assessment form and analyzed descriptively using frequencies and percentages. **Results:** The mean age was 45 years, and the largest age group was 31–40 years (33.33%). Most patients were housewives (90.00%), and 56.67% belonged to the lower socioeconomic class. Stage II disease was the most common, 50.00%, while 80.00% presented with stage II–IV disease. Half had symptoms for at least one year before seeking medical advice, including 20.00% with symptoms for more than two years. Diagnostic delay was mainly attributed to patient- or family-level factors (70.00%), followed by system- or provider-level factors (23.33%). The leading recorded cause was delayed action or neglect by patients and relatives (46.67%). Treatment initiation was delayed in 26.67% of cases, mainly because patients were unfit for operation or therapy (37.50%) or had used kabiraji or homeopathic treatment (37.50%). **Conclusion:** Delay in invasive cervical carcinoma care was most

prominent before first medical consultation. Patient/family-level barriers predominated, but system/provider-related factors and treatment-readiness issues also contributed. Strengthening awareness, screening quality, early clinical recognition, and referral pathways may reduce avoidable delay.

Keywords: Cervical cancer; Diagnostic delay; Treatment delay; Patient delay; Bangladesh.

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INTRODUCTION

Cervical cancer remains a major preventable malignancy and a persistent cause of cancer-related mortality among women, especially in low- and middle-income countries. Globally, an estimated 660,000 women were diagnosed with cervical cancer in 2022, and about 350,000 died from the disease, with most deaths occurring in settings where access to vaccination, screening, diagnostic confirmation, referral, and treatment remains limited [1]. The global strategy for elimination of cervical cancer emphasizes 90% human papillomavirus vaccination coverage, 70% screening coverage with a high-performance test, and treatment of 90% of women with precancerous lesions or invasive disease by 2030 [2]. These targets highlight that cervical cancer control depends not only on screening availability, but also on timely movement through the diagnostic and treatment pathway. In Bangladesh, the burden remains substantial. The ICO/IARC HPV Information Centre estimated that 8,268 women are diagnosed with cervical cancer and 4,971 die from the disease each year, and cervical cancer ranks as the second most frequent cancer among

Bangladeshi women [3]. Delay in cervical cancer care is a multidimensional process. It may begin with delayed recognition of symptoms, continue through delayed first consultation, be prolonged by missed or incorrect diagnosis, and extend further through referral and treatment-start barriers. A systematic review by Allahqoli et al. showed that delayed cervical cancer diagnosis is influenced by patient-related, disease-related, medical-history-related, and health-system factors [4]. Similarly, the scoping review by Nnaji et al., emphasized that timeliness of diagnosis for breast and cervical cancers in low- and middle-income countries is shaped by symptom appraisal, health literacy, socioeconomic barriers, provider practices, and health-system readiness [5]. Another related systematic review by Nnaji et al., further indicated that interventions to improve timely diagnosis are feasible in resource-limited settings, but require context-specific identification of delay points [6]. Evidence from South Asia and other resource-constrained settings shows that both patient and system factors contribute to late diagnosis and delayed treatment. In Bangladesh, Hoque et al., reported median primary, secondary, and

tertiary delays of 45, 45, and 60 days, respectively, among women with cervical cancer, with lack of knowledge, economic barriers, and healthcare-facility issues significantly associated with delay [7]. Akhter et al., also from Bangladesh, described patient-related delay, healthcare-provider delay, and healthcare-system infrastructure delay among women with advanced cervical cancer, identifying lack of awareness, low income, rural residence, nonperformance of speculum examination, misdiagnosis, repeated consultations, distance from tertiary care, and limited infrastructure as important contributors [8]. In Nepal, Gyenwali et al. estimated multiple components of diagnostic delay among women with cervical cancer, while Somanna et al., reported substantial time from self-detection of symptoms to definitive care among Indian patients [9,10]. Studies from wider low- and middle-income settings support the same care-pathway perspective. Mumba et al. documented diagnostic and treatment delays in a large hospital-based study in Zambia [11]. Mimouni et al. examined cervical cancer care-pathway delays in Morocco, while Tjokroprawiro et al. described prolonged

diagnostic and treatment journeys among patients in Indonesia [12,13]. In Kenya, Mwenda et al. found that travel cost, anxiety over cancer-care cost, older age, and diagnostic-process factors were associated with late diagnosis [14]. Collectively, these studies indicate that delay is not confined to one step; it reflects the interaction between patient behavior, family decision-making, economic capacity, provider recognition, referral processes, and treatment readiness. The present study was conducted to describe patient- and system-level delays in the diagnosis and treatment of invasive cervical carcinoma among women managed at tertiary-care centres in Bangladesh, with attention to symptom duration, diagnostic intervals, treatment initiation, and documented reasons for delay.

METHODS & MATERIALS

This descriptive observational study was conducted from January to June 2008 in the oncology units of the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology at Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University and Dhaka Medical College Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh. The study included 30 admitted women with histologically confirmed invasive carcinoma of the cervix. Patients of all ages and clinical stages were eligible after histopathological confirmation, while patients with cervical intraepithelial

neoplasia, non-invasive lesions, or diagnoses other than invasive cervical carcinoma were excluded. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and clinical assessment form. Information was recorded on sociodemographic characteristics, presenting symptoms, clinical findings, stage, histological type and grade, treatment, symptom duration, diagnostic intervals, treatment interval, and documented causes of delay. All patients underwent history taking, general and pelvic examination, clinical staging, and cervical biopsy for histopathological confirmation. Treatment decisions were made by the treating clinical team according to disease stage and patient condition. The main variables were delays across the care pathway. Patient interval was defined as the duration of symptoms before seeking medical advice and was categorized as less than 1 year, 1–2 years, or more than 2 years. Diagnostic and treatment intervals included the time from first reporting to clinical diagnosis, clinical diagnosis to confirmed diagnosis, and confirmed diagnosis to treatment initiation. Causes of diagnostic delay were grouped into patient/family-level factors, including delayed action by patients or relatives, economic crisis, and use of kabiraji or homeopathic treatment; and system/provider-level factors, including false-negative screening, failure of early diagnosis by doctors, and malpractice.

Treatment delay and its causes were also recorded. Data were compiled and analyzed descriptively using Microsoft Excel. Categorical variables were summarized as frequencies and percentages. Percentages were calculated using 30 patients as the denominator unless otherwise stated. For treatment-delay causes, percentages were calculated both among all patients and among delayed cases. No inferential statistical testing was performed because of the small sample size and descriptive study design.

RESULTS

A total of 30 women with histologically confirmed invasive carcinoma of the cervix were included in the study. The age of the patients ranged from 20 to 70 years, with a mean age of 45 years. The largest proportion of patients belonged to the 31–40-year age group, 10 patients, 33.33%, followed by the 41–50-year age group, 9 patients, 30.00%. All patients were married, and 2 patients, 6.67%, were widowed. Most patients were housewives, 27 patients, 90.00%. More than half of the patients belonged to the lower socioeconomic class, 17 patients, 56.67%, while 10 patients, 33.33%, were from the middle socioeconomic class. Regarding educational status, 12 patients, 40.00%, were illiterate, and 10 patients, 33.33%, had completed only primary education (*Table I*).

Table I

Baseline sociodemographic characteristics of the study population, $n=30$.

Variable	Category	Number	Percentage
Age group, years	20–30	2	6.67
	31–40	10	33.33
	41–50	9	30.00
	51–60	4	13.33
	61–70	5	16.67
Marital status	Married	30	100.00
	Widow	2	6.67
Occupation	Housewife	27	90.00
	Service holder	3	10.00
Socioeconomic status	Rich	2	6.67
	Upper middle class	1	3.33
	Middle class	10	33.33
	Lower class	17	56.67
Educational status	Illiterate	12	40.00
	Primary	10	33.33
	Secondary	6	20.00
	Higher education	2	6.67

Back pain was the most frequently recorded symptom, reported by 22 patients, 73.33%, followed by post-coital bleeding in 19 patients, 63.33%. Post-coital bleeding was the most frequent bleeding-related presenting symptom. Foul-smelling per-

vaginal discharge was reported by 14 patients, 46.67%, and blood-stained per-vaginal discharge by 12 patients, 40.00%. Back pain was reported by 22 patients, 73.33%. Urinary difficulty was present in 12 patients, 40.00%, while difficulty in

defecation was present in 5 patients, 16.67%. Postmenopausal bleeding was documented in 2 patients, 6.67%. These symptoms frequently coexisted (*Table II*).

Table II

Presenting symptoms among patients with invasive cervical carcinoma, *n*=30.

Presenting symptom	Number	Percentage
Back pain	22	73.33
Post-coital bleeding	19	63.33
Foul-smelling per-vaginal discharge	14	46.67
Blood-stained per-vaginal discharge	12	40.00
Difficulty in micturition	12	40.00
Difficulty in defecation	5	16.67
Postmenopausal bleeding	2	6.67

Note: Multiple responses were present; percentages therefore do not total 100%.

Stage II disease was the most common stage at presentation, observed in 15 patients, 50.00%. Stage III disease was present in 7 patients, 23.33%, stage I in 6 patients, 20.00%, and stage IV in 2 patients, 6.67%. Squamous cell carcinoma was the predominant histological type, found in 28 patients, 93.33%, while adenocarcinoma was found in 2 patients, 6.67%. Poorly differentiated carcinoma was the most frequent histological grade, observed in 16 patients, 53.33%, followed by moderately differentiated carcinoma in 9 patients, 30.00%, and well-differentiated carcinoma in 5 patients, 16.67% (Table III).

Table III

Disease characteristics of the study population, *n*=30.

Variable	Category	Number	Percentage
Clinical stage	Stage I	6	20.00
	Stage II	15	50.00
	Stage III	7	23.33
	Stage IV	2	6.67
Histological type	Squamous cell carcinoma	28	93.33
	Adenocarcinoma	2	6.67
Histological grade	Well differentiated	5	16.67
	Moderately differentiated	9	30.00
	Poorly differentiated	16	53.33

The duration of symptoms before seeking medical advice was less than 1 year in 15 patients, 50.00%. Nine patients, 30.00%, had symptoms for 1–2 years before seeking care, and 6 patients, 20.00%, had symptoms for more than 2 years. Overall, 15 patients, 50.00%, had a symptom duration of at least 1 year before first seeking medical advice. This represents a substantial patient interval before entry into formal healthcare (Table IV).

Table IV

Duration of symptoms before seeking medical advice, *n*=30.

Duration of symptoms before seeking medical advice	Number	Percentage
Less than 1 year	15	50.00
1–2 years	9	30.00
More than 2 years	6	20.00
Total	30	100.00

The interval between first reporting to a health professional and clinical diagnosis was less than 6 months in 21 patients, 70.00%, and 6 months to 1 year in 5 patients, 16.67%. Among classifiable records, no patient had an interval exceeding 1 year. Four cases, 13.33%, had no classifiable interval in the tabulated dataset. The interval between clinical diagnosis and confirmed diagnosis was less than 6 months in 28 patients, 93.33%, and 6 months to 1 year in 2 patients, 6.67%. No patient had a recorded interval exceeding 1 year between clinical diagnosis and confirmed diagnosis. The interval between confirmed diagnosis and treatment initiation followed the same distribution: 28 patients, 93.33%, received treatment within 6 months of confirmed diagnosis, and 2 patients, 6.67%, received treatment within 6 months to 1 year. The original thesis table recorded the diagnosis and treatment interval distributions, along with causes of diagnostic and treatment delay (Table V).

Table V

Diagnostic and treatment pathway intervals, *n*=30.

Care-pathway interval	<6 months	6 months–1 year	>1 year	Not classifiable	Total
First reporting to clinical diagnosis	21, 70.00%	5, 16.67%	0, 0.00%	4, 13.33%	30, 100.00%
Clinical diagnosis to confirmed diagnosis	28, 93.33%	2, 6.67%	0, 0.00%	0, 0.00%	30, 100.00%
Confirmed diagnosis to treatment initiation	28, 93.33%	2, 6.67%	0, 0.00%	0, 0.00%	30, 100.00%

Note: The first reporting-to-clinical diagnosis interval was classifiable for 26 patients. Four patients were retained in the denominator as not classifiable.

The most frequently recorded cause of delay in diagnosis was delayed action or neglect by the patient and relatives, documented in 14 patients, 46.67%. False-negative screening test results and use of kabiraji or

homeopathic treatment were each recorded in 4 patients, 13.33%. Economic crisis was recorded in 3 patients, 10.00%. Provider-related causes included failure of the doctor to diagnose early in 2 patients, 6.67%, and

malpractice of the doctor in 1 patient, 3.33%. No specific diagnostic-delay cause was recorded for 2 patients, 6.67% (Table VI).

Table VI
Recorded causes of delay in diagnosis, n=30.

Cause of delay in diagnosis	Number	Percentage
Delayed action or neglect by patient and relatives	14	46.67
False-negative screening test	4	13.33
Taking kabiraji or homeopathic treatment	4	13.33
Economic crisis	3	10.00
Failure of doctor to diagnose early	2	6.67
Malpractice of doctor	1	3.33
No specific cause recorded	2	6.67
Total	30	100.00

After grouping the recorded causes of diagnostic delay, patient/family-level contributors accounted for 21 cases, 70.00%. These included delayed action or neglect by patients and relatives, economic

crisis, and prior use of kabiraji or homeopathic treatment. System/provider-level contributors accounted for 7 cases, 23.33%, including false-negative screening test, failure of the doctor to diagnose early,

and malpractice of the doctor. Two cases, 6.67%, had no specific cause recorded (Table VII).

Table VII
Reclassified domains of diagnostic delay, n=30.

Delay domain	Included causes	Number	Percentage
Patient/family-level delay	Delayed action or neglect by patient and relatives; economic crisis; kabiraji or homeopathic treatment	21	70.00
System/provider-level delay	False-negative screening test; failure of doctor to diagnose early; malpractice of doctor	7	23.33
Not specified	No specific cause recorded	2	6.67
Total		30	100.00

Delayed treatment initiation was recorded in 8 patients, 26.67%. The remaining 22

patients, 73.33%, received treatment without recorded delay (Table VIII).

Table VIII
Treatment initiation status, n=30.

Treatment initiation status	Number	Percentage
Delayed treatment	8	26.67
Treatment without recorded delay	22	73.33
Total	30	100.00

Among patients with delayed treatment initiation, being unfit for operation or therapy and prior use of kabiraji or homeopathic treatment were the most

common causes, each reported in 3 patients, accounting for 37.50% of delayed cases. Financial cause and malpractice of doctor

were each reported in 1 patient, accounting for 12.50% of delayed cases (Table IX).

Table IX
Causes of treatment delay, n=30.

Cause of treatment delay	Number	Percentage of total sample, N=30	Percentage among delayed cases, n=8
Not fit for operation or therapy	3	10.00	37.50
Taking kabiraji or homeopathic treatment	3	10.00	37.50
Financial cause	1	3.33	12.50
Malpractice of doctor	1	3.33	12.50
Total delayed cases	8	26.67	100.00

DISCUSSION

The present study described patient- and system-level delays among women with invasive cervical carcinoma managed at tertiary-care centres in Bangladesh. The most important observation was that delay was concentrated before entry into formal medical care. Half of the patients had

symptoms for at least one year before seeking medical advice, including 20.00% who had symptoms for more than two years. This prolonged patient interval is longer than that reported in several recent South Asian studies using day-based delay definitions. In Nepal, Gyenwali et al. reported a median patient delay of 68.5 days

and a median total diagnostic delay of 157 days, while in India, Somanna et al. found a median interval of 80 days from self-detection of symptoms to first contact with a general physician^[9,10]. The much longer interval in the present series may reflect the historical period of data collection, lower awareness of cervical cancer symptoms,

limited screening access, family-level decision barriers, and delayed referral to tertiary care. However, the direction of the finding is consistent with regional evidence showing that delay before diagnosis is common among women with cervical cancer. Patient/family-level contributors were the dominant documented causes of diagnostic delay, accounting for 70.00% of cases. The most frequent individual cause was delayed action or neglect by patients and relatives, recorded in 46.67%. Similar patient-level barriers have been reported in Bangladesh and other low-resource settings. Hoque et al. found that primary delay among Bangladeshi women with cervical cancer was significantly associated with personal factors, including lack of knowledge, while Akhter et al. identified lack of awareness, low income, rural residence, embarrassment, fear, and delayed discussion with family members as important contributors to treatment initiation delay [7,8]. In India, Somanna et al. reported lack of awareness as the major reason for not seeking care after symptom detection. These findings suggest that delayed care-seeking is often not simple refusal or neglect, but may represent poor symptom appraisal, low perceived severity, family dependence, financial insecurity, and limited cancer literacy [9]. Use of kabiraji or homeopathic treatment was documented as a cause of diagnostic delay in 13.33% of patients and as a cause of treatment delay in 37.50% of delayed-treatment cases. This is an important culturally relevant finding. In Bangladesh, informal and traditional care pathways may be accessed before formal oncological care, particularly when symptoms are initially interpreted as benign gynaecological problems. Comparable findings have been reported elsewhere. Tjokropawiro et al. observed that treatment delays among Indonesian patients were related partly to social barriers and the use of alternative medicine, while Chadza et al. reported that women in Malawi delayed hospital care because of individual beliefs and health-facility barriers, including reliance on non-formal pathways before reaching tertiary facilities [13,15]. Zeleke et al. also identified traditional healer use and low awareness as factors associated with delayed diagnosis in Ethiopia [16]. These findings support the need to engage community-level providers and improve public recognition of warning symptoms such as post-coital bleeding, abnormal discharge, and persistent pelvic or back pain. System/provider-level contributors accounted for 23.33% of diagnostic-delay categories, including false-negative screening, failure of early diagnosis by doctors, and malpractice. Although less frequent than patient/family-level delay in this dataset, these findings remain clinically important. In Nepal, Gyenwali et al. found

that 90% of patients experienced healthcare-provider delay greater than one week, indicating that provider-related delay can be substantial in South Asian care pathways [10]. Akhter et al. also reported provider-related factors in Bangladesh, including nonperformance of speculum examination, misdiagnosis, repeated consultations, and delayed referral [8]. The present finding should therefore be interpreted as evidence that patient delay and system delay coexist, rather than as competing explanations. Rakhshanda et al. showed that cervical cancer service readiness in Bangladesh varies across facility levels, with gaps in trained staff, guidelines, equipment, diagnostic capacity, and treatment readiness outside higher-level facilities [17]. This supports the possibility that women may experience delays before reaching tertiary-care centres where diagnosis and treatment are more available. Treatment delay was recorded in 26.67% of patients. Among delayed-treatment cases, the two leading causes were being unfit for operation or therapy and prior use of kabiraji or homeopathic treatment, each accounting for 37.50%. This finding indicates that treatment delay was not only an administrative or financial problem; it also reflected advanced clinical condition and diversion through alternative care pathways. Similar care-pathway delays have been reported in other low- and middle-income countries. Mumba et al. documented long time to treatment initiation in Zambia and found that public-sector diagnostic and referral pathways contributed to prolonged turnaround time [11]. In Indonesia, Tjokropawiro et al. reported that 51.2% of patients received first therapy more than 12 months after symptom onset [13]. Compared with these studies, the present treatment-delay proportion appears lower, but direct comparison is limited because the present dataset used broad categories, especially “less than six months,” rather than precise day-based intervals. Most patients in this study presented beyond stage I, with 80.00% diagnosed at stage II–IV and stage II being the most common stage, 50.00%. This pattern is consistent with previous evidence from Bangladesh and other low-resource settings. Ferdous et al. reported stage II as the most frequent presentation among Bangladeshi patients with invasive cervical cancer, while Mumba et al. found stage II to be the most common stage in Zambia [11,18]. In Ethiopia, Dereje et al. found advanced-stage diagnosis to be associated with diagnostic interval greater than 90 days, out-of-pocket payment, non-immediate action after symptom recognition, and multiple facility visits before diagnostic confirmation [19]. The predominance of stage II–IV disease in the present study is therefore compatible with the observed delay profile and reinforces

that earlier symptom recognition, timely pelvic examination, reliable screening pathways, and efficient referral are central to improving cervical cancer outcomes in Bangladesh. Overall, the findings indicate that delays in invasive cervical carcinoma care are distributed across the pathway, but the most pronounced delay occurred before first medical consultation. Patient/family-level barriers predominated, while system/provider-level factors and treatment-readiness barriers also contributed. These results support a combined intervention strategy involving community awareness, family-level counselling, discouragement of harmful diagnostic delay through non-formal care pathways, provider training for early recognition, strengthening of screening quality, and more efficient referral from peripheral facilities to tertiary centres.

LIMITATIONS

This study was limited by its small sample size and descriptive observational design, which restricted the ability to perform inferential analysis or identify independent predictors of delay. The delay intervals were recorded in broad categories rather than exact days or weeks, limiting precise estimation of diagnostic and treatment timelines. Some interval data were not fully classifiable, particularly the interval between first reporting and clinical diagnosis.

CONCLUSION

Patient- and system-level delays were evident in the diagnostic and treatment pathway of women with invasive cervical carcinoma. The most prominent delay occurred before first medical consultation, as half of the patients had symptoms for at least one year before seeking medical advice. Patient and family-level factors were the dominant contributors to diagnostic delay, particularly delayed action by patients and relatives, economic crisis, and use of kabiraji or homeopathic treatment. System and provider-related factors, including false-negative screening and delayed clinical recognition, also contributed. Treatment delay affected more than one-fourth of patients and was mainly related to clinical unfitness for treatment and prior use of kabiraji or homeopathic treatment. These findings emphasize the need for improved community awareness, early symptom recognition, timely pelvic examination, quality-assured screening, and efficient referral to tertiary-care services.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None declared

ETHICAL APPROVAL

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee

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